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Radiation Risks Assessment With Its Biological Effect Using 16 CT Slice Scanner In Adult Brain Procedure In A Private Diagnostic Center In Port-Harcourt, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Computed tomography (CT) has become an indispensable tool in modern medical diagnostics; however, its use involves exposure to ionizing radiation, which carries potential health risks. This study aimed to evaluate the radiation doses and associated risks in adult patients undergoing brain CT scans using 16-slice CT scanners in a private diagnostic center located in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. A total of twenty (20) adult patients were assessed and examined in the facility. Environmental background radiation levels were measured, and patient doses were determined using thermoluminescent dosimeters (TLDs). Parameters such as the absorbed dose, effective dose, dose length product (DLP), volume CT dose index (CTDIvol), lifetime cancer risk, and hereditary risk were evaluated. The findings revealed considerable variation in radiation doses across the facility, with some values exceeding international diagnostic reference levels (DRLs). The highest patient dose recorded was 2.34 mSv, with a corresponding lifetime cancer risk of 0.1287×10^{-3} , while the lowest was 0.48 mSv with a life time cancer risks of 0.0264×10^{-3} . Mean background radiation values remained within acceptable limits, yet highlighted areas for radiation protection improvement. This study emphasizes the need for adherence to the ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) principle, the establishment of local DRLs, and implementation of effective radiation dose optimization strategies to safeguard patient health without compromising diagnostic efficacy.

Keywords: CT brain, DRL assessments, radiation risks, cancer and heredity

INTRODUCTION

Computed tomography (CT) is a radiologic modality that provides clinical information in the detection, differentiation, and demarcation of disease and delineation of anatomy. Hence, it is the primary diagnostic modality for a variety of clinical problems and is widely accepted as a supplement to other imaging techniques (Robinson et al., 2024).

There are different types of computed tomography machine, which is based on its make, model, specification and the uniqueness of its component. Some of the machines are made up of detectors and

slices numbering 2, 16, 64, 128 and 520 which are referred to as the computed tomography modalities of which in the context of this study 16 slices are referred to as the CT modality.

However, one of the commonest parts of the body which the machine is used to investigate is the brain and its content. During the procedure the patient's head is placed inside the gantry of the machine and with appropriate protocol the brain and its content is been investigated for tumours, infection, or intracranial bleeding. During the use of the CT machine, some quantity of radiation is deposited on the tissues directly or as scatter radiation. This radiation that is deposited on the tissues of the patient is the radiation dose. Therefore, radiation dose is the quantity of radiation deposited per unit body mass and the amount of radiation deposited on the body tissues is associated with some risk and danger (Bushberg *et al.*, 2020). According to the United Nations environment Annual Report (2016), the use of ionizing radiation in medical practice is the greatest means of exposure to ionizing radiation among humans.

There is some health risk associated with radiation exposure. Knowing what the associated risks will help regulatory bodies to set dose limits and regulations that will limit exposure to a tolerable and acceptable risk levels (Radiation Health Effects Canadian website).

United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR, 2000) was established in 1955. Since after its establishment (UNSCEAR) committee has undertaken a very broad assessment of the radiation sources and ionizing radiation effects on humans and the environment. Those assessments have provided the relevant information that is used in the formulation of international standards for radiation protection purposes for radiation workers and the general public.

In the past 10 years due to the increasing relevance of CT in medical practice, the use of computed tomography has rapidly increased in the United States of America (USA) and globally (Pearce, 2011). This imaging modality uses ionizing radiation in the form of x-rays which are produced when fast-moving high-energy electrons strike a tungsten target (Sulleman *et al.*, 2011; Noriko *et al.*, 2020; Bushberg *et al.*, 2020).

Epidemiologic and biologic researches reveal that there exists strong evidence to support the fact that there is an increased risk of cancers in humans following exposure to moderate and high-level exposure to ionizing radiation (Pearce *et al.*, 2012). The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC, 2012) has therefore classified ionizing radiation as a Group 1 Carcinogen ("carcinogenic to humans"). It is also referred to as universal carcinogen because of its potential to induce most types of malignancies (IARC, 2012).

Many in the field of radiodiagnosis and medical physics are becoming worried about the higher radiation doses used in CT and nuclear imaging regarding the potential anticipated complications (Ron, 2003; Gibson *et al.*, 2014). These concerns about the adverse impact of radiation dose and a world-wide trend towards the increasing collective radiation dose (Ron, 2003; Gibson *et al.*, 2014) led to the formulation of guidelines advising on the indications for CT scanning and radiation dose (Wall, 2005; ARPANSA, 2011) which also led to the development of new modalities that reduces time of exposure and dose.

Ionizing radiation has the potential to damage DNA and this may result to DNA mutations which could occur following DNA mis-repair of the earlier damaged tissue (Radiation risk from medical imaging). The evaluation of the survivors of the atomic bomb blast revealed a significant increase in cancer risk with exposure to ionizing radiation (Radiation risk from medical imaging). The probability of developing radiation risk increases with the exposure amount, number of exposures, and with younger age group (Donald *et al.*, 2017). Computed tomography risks are small but if these small risks are produced by million numbers of scans, they may drive into serious public health concerns in the future.

The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) has adjusted the nominal radiological detriment coefficients for cancer and hereditary effects as follows: 5.5×10^{-2} and $0.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Sv}^{-1}$ for the whole population. Having an awareness of typical dose levels enables CT practitioners to promptly recognize and rectify any protocols that do not adhere to the ALARA principle (As Low As Reasonably Achievable principle), thus improving radiographic procedures.

Study on Assessment of the radiation dose during 16 slices CT examination (Mkimel *et al.*;2019) obtained Effective dose of 0.71 mSv (male) and 0.76 mSv for female. In a study (Kojimahara *et al.*; 2020), the absorbed doses recorded in the three modalities 16, 64 and 128 slices CT scanner whose work assessed skull CT and incidence of brain cancer/tumour throughout infancy and adolescence, the mean assessed brain dosage was 32 ± 13 mGy (equivalent to 32 ± 13 mSv).

The objective of the study is assessment of radiation risk associated with the use of the computed tomography scan with 16 slice CT machine, as well as to analyze the associated biological effects in adults. The study will further address pertinent concerns centered on patient's safety by suggesting radiation exposure reference levels, thereby contributing to the advancements in the field of medical imaging by promoting responsible and evidence-based healthcare decisions without compromising diagnostic precision.

METHOD

The study was an empirical study conducted at the Image Diagnostic Radiology tagged as Facility A in this study, with patients referred for brain CT scan using a 16 Slice Siemens SOMATOM Definition Flash CT scanning system from October 2024 to March 2025. Participants were counseled; informed consent and ethical approval were obtained before the commencement of examination. The age, height and weight of the patients were obtained and documented prior to the investigation. Other exposure-related parameters such as gantry tilt, tube current (mA), exposure time, tension (kV), slice thickness, number of slices, table increment, and the dose length product DLP (mGy.cm), as well as started and finished locations on the displayed CT dose index $CTDI_{vol}$ (mGy), were taken into account. The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) conversion factor was used to evaluate the effective dose and DRL.

The examination was performed in accordance with standard protocols for brain CT scan. Radiation dose was measured with a coded thermoluminescent dosimeter chip (TLD) chip (TLD LiF-100) which has been previously annealed to wipe out previous data. The TLD chip was placed on the glabella being the centering point and held in position with a transparent (radiolucent) adhesive tape before the exposures. The sample population was sixty –seven (67) being the number of brain CT examination performed within 6 months duration at the private radio-diagnostic facility study center in Port Harcourt. To eliminate bias, a randomized sampling method was adopted with a sample size of twenty (20) which was derived from the sample population. After the completion of the examination, the TLD was immediately removed and labeled appropriately against the patient's coded number and carefully sealed in tiny transparent cellophane bag with the coded number of the patient to maintain confidentiality. The transparent cellophane bag was later inserted into a black bag to prevent spurious exposures from background radiation. The TLD's were then sent for reading at the radiation dosimetry laboratory of the Regional Centre for Energy Research and Training (CERT).

Body mass index (BMI) of participants was obtained from the participant's weight and height. by dividing the weight (kg) by square of the height (m^2). The effective doses were estimated by multiplying the absorbed dose by the weighting factor. The cancer and hereditary risk per procedure were estimated by multiplying the effective dose with the cancer and hereditary risk factor coefficients of $5.5 \times 10^{-2} Sv^{-1}$ and $0.2 \times 10^{-2} Sv^{-1}$ respectively. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) windows version 22.30 statistical software (SPSS Inc, Chicago, Illinois, USA) was used to analyse the data and the results presented in tables, charts and graphs.

The arithmetic mean (also denoted as mean) and third quartile (75th percentile) are used to express quantitative variables. Descriptive statistics were used to evaluate the CT data.

Average $CTDI_{vol}$ (mGy) for each sequence and total DLP per examination were calculated. The typical dose was estimated using median DLP and $CTDI_{vol}$ (mGy) data. The rounded third quartile values of median distributions for $CTDI_{vol}$ (mGy) and DLP (mGy.cm) data were used to set the DRL for the diagnostic center.

The estimated Effective Dose (E) in Sievert (Sv) is obtained by multiplying the absorbed dose by a brain-specific conversion factor (k) of 0.0021 as recommended by the International Commission on Radiological Protection.

$$E \text{ (mSv)} = \text{DLP} \times K_{\text{brain}} \text{ (for adults)} \quad (1)$$

The Radiation Cancer risk was estimated following each procedure. The cancer risk (R_{CR}) per procedure was obtained by multiplying the effective dose (E_{eff}) with the risk coefficients (F_{CR}). $F_{CR} = 5.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Sv}^{-1}$ obtained from ICRP 103 as stated in equation (2) below.

$$R_{CR} = F_{CR} \times E_{eff} \quad (2)$$

Hereditary risk being the radiation risk of genetic effects (R_{GE}) was evaluated by multiplying the mean dose by the risk factor coefficients $F_{GE} = 0.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Sv}^{-1}$ obtained from ICRP 103 publication as shown in equation 3.

$$R_{GR} = F_{GE} \times E_{eff} \quad (3)$$

RESULTS

Table 1 represents the data obtained as a result of TLDs sent for measurement at the Radiation Dosimetric Laboratory with dosimetric result for Image diagnostic center tagged as Facility A while Table 2 represent the machine and patient-based parameters obtained at Image diagnostic center, Table 3 present Statistical Table Showing Diagnostic Reference levels for Facility A.

Tables 4 presents gender distribution of absorbed doses from TLD reading during 16 CT scanner procedures while Table 5a and Table 5b presents female and male distribution of doses from TLD with the associated radiological risks during 16 slice CT scanner clinical procedure respectively. Table 6 shows Comparison of Effective dose with other studies according to ICDR 103 recommendations. Table 7 presents comparison of DLP of 16 slices CT scanner during clinical procedure with ICRP value. The relationship between individuals' age, BMI, and cancer risk and radiation exposures to the brain is shown in Table 8

The absorbed doses of twenty (20) patients recorded from the TLD readings during 16 slices CT scanner procedure is presented on Table 1. From Table 1, patient absorbed radiation dose (in mSv) ranges from 0.48 mSv to 2.34 mSv in facility A where 16 slices CT scanner machine was used. Maximum radiation dose of 2.34 mSv was recorded by patient 7 while the lowest dose 0.48 mSv was recorded by patient 4.

The mean exposure parameters for the 16 slice CT scanner in Facility A were: kVp = 110, mAs = 25, CTDI = 38.95mGy, and DLP = 760.14 mGy-cm from Table 2. In terms of dosimetry, the Computed Tomography Dose Index Volume (CTDIvol) was observed to fluctuate between 38.89 and 39.401 mGy, averaging at 38.96 mGy. Additionally, the Dose Length Product (DLP) for each scan showed a variation from 656.19 to 894.16 mGy.cm, with an average of 764.41mGy.

Table 4 shows patient absorbed dosage of radiation for both genders using 16 slice CT scanner. In facility A, absorbed dose among the females (2.34 ± 0.02 mSv) was more than what the men got. (2.01 ± 0.66 mSv). These results might be explained by the subjects' BMI, which shows the same gender disparity as the absorbed dosage.

From table 5a, the female patient absorbed radiation dose (mSv) ranged from 0.48 mSv to 2.34 mSv with the age of female patients studied ranges from 26 to 77 years old with the associated risks. Table 5b presents the male absorbed radiation dose ranges from 0.66 mSv to 2.10 mSv with the age of male patients studied in facility A ranges from 30 to 64 years old and their associated risks.

The effective dose of the female patients in facility A ranges from 1.378 to 1.702 mSv. Two female patients of 28 and 45 years old recorded the maximum effective dose of 1.702 mSv. The mean effective

doses employing 16 slice CT were 1.3 ± 0.081 mSv, whereas the maximum effective dose were 1.702 mSv. Table 4.24 illustrates that the mean effective dose among females using the 16 slice CT was 1.32 ± 0.075 mSv, but among the men, that was 0.94 ± 0.16 mSv

. In the comparison of Effective dose with other studies according to ICDR 103 recommendations in Table 6, female effective dose ranges within the values obtained from other studies except for view female patients that are higher while male effective doses are higher than values obtained from others studies but are below the ICDR103 recommendations.

The index study's scatter plots of patients' absorbed radiation dosage and BMI at facility "A" showed a patterned distribution that shows a linear link between the two variables. This implies that, in facility A, the radiation dosage and body mass index (BMI) are related.

Correlation analysis (Table 7) in Facility A indicated a weak positive correlation between effective dose and mAs ($r = 0.100$), and between effective dose and DLP ($r = 0.159$), but no correlation between effective dose and CTDI. kVp showed strong positive correlation with mAs ($r = 0.689$) and CTDI ($r = 0.895$), and a moderate correlation with DLP ($r = 0.252$), but no correlation with effective dose.

The amount of radiation administered to patients with corresponding estimated risk assessed using a 16-slice CT revealed that cancer risk varies from 2.09×10^{-5} to 3.74×10^{-5} , having greatest risk of roughly 4 persons in 10,000 (3.74×10^{-5}).

Table 1: Dosimetric result from Image Diagnostic centre (IDC)

S/N	Chips ID	Dose (mSv)	Lifetime Cancer Risk $\times 10^{-3}$
1	Patient 01	0.56	0.0308
2	Patient 02	1.74	0.0957
3	Patient 03	0.76	0.0418
4	Patient 04	0.48	0.0264
5	Patient 05	1.39	0.0764
6	Patient 06	1.18	0.0649
7	Patient 07	2.34	0.1287
8	Patient 08	0.74	0.0407
9	Patient 09	0.82	0.0451
10	Patient 10	0.78	0.0429
11	Patient 11	0.95	0.0522
12	Patient 12	0.68	0.0374
13	Patient 13	2.33	0.1282
14	Patient 14	2.28	0.1254
15	Patient 15	1.25	0.0688
16	Patient 16	0.64	0.0352
17	Patient 17	2.04	0.112
18	Patient 18	0.66	0.0363
19	Patient 19	2.01	0.111
20	Patient 20	1.38	0.0759
	Mean	1.19	0.0688

Using *ICRP 103 model*, Max Dose = 2.34 mSv (Patient 07), Min Dose = 0.48 mSv (Patient 04)

Table 2: Machine and Some Physical parameters from Image Diagnostic centre (IDC)

S/N	Age	Gender	kVp	mAs	H Cm	W kg	CTDI _v	DLP	Eff dose (mSv)	Life time Cancer risk	BMI
1	38	Female	110	25	159	87	38.89	697.69	1.47	0.081	34.42
2	28	Female	110	25	156	76	38.89	810.47	1.70	0.094	31.24
3	45	Female	110	25	157	86	38.89	810.47	1.70	0.094	34.87
4	72	Female	110	25	163	56	38.89	724.91	1.52	0.084	1.00
5	40	Female	110	25	167	89	38.89	724.91	1.52	0.084	1.92
6	46	Male	110	25	172	70	39.01	771.27	1.62	0.089	3.66
7	58	Female	110	25	153	61	39.01	722.51	1.52	0.083	6.06
8	57	Female	110	25	147	82	39.01	745.91	1.57	0.086	7.95
9	77	Female	110	25	161	73	39.01	763.47	1.60	0.088	8.16
10	64	Male	110	25	180	98	38.89	746.30	1.57	0.086	0.25
11	26	Female	110	25	169	83	39.01	796.63	1.67	0.092	9.06
12	30	Male	110	25	175	79	39.01	786.88	1.65	0.091	5.80
13	65	Female	110	25	155	65	39.01	779.63	1.64	0.090	7.06
14	34	Female	110	25	163	77	38.89	778.35	1.64	0.090	8.98
15	42	Male	110	25	167	84	39.01	812.23	1.71	0.094	0.13
16	38	Female	110	25	155	94	39.01	656.19	1.38	0.076	9.14
17	60	Female	110	25	159	67	39.01	720.56	1.51	0.083	6.49
18	62	Male	110	25	168	76	38.89	831.86	1.75	0.096	6.93
19	38	Male	110	25	173	78	39.01	894.16	1.88	0.103	6.06
20	51	Female	110	25	156	108	39.01	708.85	1.61	0.082	4.39

Table 3: Statistical Table Showing Diagnostic Reference levels for Facility A

Parameter	CTDI _v (mGy)	DLP (mGy·cm)
Mean	38.95	760.14
Median (50th %ile)	39.01	771.27
Mode	38.89, 39.01 (Bimodal)	810.47, 724.91 (Bimodal)
Range	0.12 (39.01 - 38.89)	237.97 (894.16 - 656.19)
Standard Deviation	0.05	59.07
Variance	0.0025	3489.07
25th Percentile (Q1)	38.89	724.91
75th Percentile (Q3)	39.01	810.47
Interquartile Range (IQR)	0.12 (Q3 - Q1)	85.56 (Q3 - Q1)

Table 4: Gender Distribution of absorbed doses of Patients from TLD Readings during 16 slice (Image Diagnostic Center) CT scanner procedure

S/N	FEMALE			MALE		
	Age (yrs)	BMI	Radiation Dose (mSv)	Age (yrs)	BMI	Radiation Dose (mSv)
1	38	34.42	0.56	46	23.66	1.18
2	28	31.24	1.74	64	30.25	0.78
3	45	34.87	0.76	30	25.80	0.68
4	72	21.00	0.48	42	30.13	1.25
5	40	31.92	1.39	62	26.49	0.66
	58	26.06	2.34	38	26.06	2.01
6						
7	57	37.95	0.74	-	-	-
8	77	28.16	0.82	-	-	-
9	26	29.06	0.95	-	-	-
10	65	27.06	2.33	-	-	-
11	34	28.98	2.28	-	-	-
12	38	39.14	0.64	-	-	-
13	60	26.93	2.04	-	-	-
14	51	44.31	1.38	-	-	-

Table 5a : Female Gender distribution of absorbed doses of Patients from TLD reading with associated cancer risk during 16 slice CT scanner (Image Diagnostic)

Chip ID	Age year	BMI (Kg/m ²)	Radiation Dose (mSv)	Effective dose (mSv)	Lifetime cancer risk x10 ⁻⁵	Hereditary Risk x10 ⁻⁶
IDC1	38		0.56	1.465	0.81	2.93
		34.42				
IDC2	28	31.24	1.74	1.702	0.94	3.40
IDC3	45	34.87	0.76	1.702	0.94	3.40
IDC4	72	21.08	0.48	1.522	0.84	3.04
IDC5	40	31.92	1.39	1.522	0.84	3.04
IDC7	58	26.06	2.34	1.517	0.83	3.03
IDC8	57	37.95	0.74	1.566	0.86	3.13
IDC9	77	28.16	0.82	1.603	0.88	3.21
		29.06				
IDC11	26	29.06	0.95	1.673	0.92	3.35
IDC13	65	27.06	2.33	1.637	0.90	3.27
IDC14	34	28.98	2.28	1.637	0.90	3.27
IDC16	38	39.14	0.64	1.378	0.76	2.76
IDC17	60	26.49	2.04	1.513	0.83	3.03
IDC20	51	44.39	1.38	1.489	0.82	2.98

Table 5b : Male Gender distribution of absorbed doses of Patients from TLD reading with associated cancer risk during 16 slice CT scanner (Image Diagnostic)

Chip ID	Age year	BMI (Kg/m ²)	Radiation Dose (mSv)	Effective Dose (mSv)	Lifetime cancer risk x 10 ⁻⁵	Hereditary Risk x 10 ⁻⁶
IDC6	46	23.66	1.18	1.620	8.10	3.24
IDC10	64	30.25	0.78	1.567	7.84	3.13
IDC12	30	25.8	0.68	1.652	8.26	3.30
IDC15	42	30.13	1.25	1.706	8.53	3.41
IDC18	62	26.93	0.66	1.747	8.74	3.49
IDC19	38	26.06	2.01	1.878	9.39	3.75

Table 6: Comparison of Effective dose with other studies according to ICDR 103 recommendations

STUDY	Obtained value mSv	±SD
Netherland (2013)	1.5	
NSRD (2010)	1.5	
HPA	1.4	
Mkimel <i>et al.</i> , 2019	0.65	
FACILITY A	1.378 – 1.702	Female
	1.567 - 1.878	Male

Table 7. Correlation between radiation dose with age, BMI and Cancer Risk of participants FACILITY A

		AGE	BMI	Absorbed Dose	Cancer Risk
AGE	Pearson Correlation	1	.186	-.007	.002
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.373	.975	.994
BMI	Pearson Correlation	.186	1	.126	.130
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.373r		.549	.535
Absorbed Dose	Pearson Correlation	-.007	.126	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.975	.549		.000
Cancer Risk	Pearson Correlation	.002	.130	1.000**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.994	.535	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figures 1 – 2 illustrate Correlation of Female and Male age with the radiation dose from 16 slices CT scanner while Figure 3 present Correlation of patient dose with BMI.

Fig.1: Correlation of Female age with the radiation dose from 16 slices CT scanner

Fig. 2 : Correlation of male age with the radiation dose from 16 slices CT scanner

Fig.3: Correlation of patient dose with BMI

Figure 1-2 illustrates the correlation between patient age and radiation dose from a 16-slice CT scanner for both genders. The analysis showed no strong correlation between age and radiation dose in either females (a) or males (b), indicating that radiation dose variations were not age-dependent.

Figure 3 presents the correlation between patient radiation dose and Body Mass Index (BMI). The analysis indicates a positive correlation, where higher BMI is associated with an increase in radiation dose, reflecting the need for higher exposure settings in patients with larger body sizes.

DISCUSSION

This descriptive study was carried out to propose DRLs for the adult CT-scan examinations at the private diagnostic center using 16 CT scanner in Port Harcourt, River state. The 75th percentile of DLP was 810.47mGy.cm and CTDI_v was 39.01mGy. The values are below the ICRP recommendation on Diagnostic Reference levels hence, shows that it was a good establishment.

The absorbed doses from 16-slice CT scanner were lower than those reported by Kojimahara et al. (2020), who found a mean brain dose of 32±13 mGy in a childhood brain tumor study. This difference may be due to the use of diagnostic reference levels and differences in study population. However, doses in the current study were higher than those in Nzotta et al. (2016), likely because their study included children, who require lower exposure settings, whereas only adults were included. Table 5 shows mean effective doses of 1.32±0.075 mSv (females) and 0.94±0.16 mSv (males) for the 16-slice CT used in this study.

The mean absorbed doses received by females were higher than that of males. Consequent upon that, the mean effective dose among females were also higher than that observed among the males. These findings may be attributed to the slightly higher BMI of the females compared to males. This finding is in consonance with a study to evaluate ‘Patient Body Mass Index and Physician Radiation Dose during Coronary Angiography’ by Madder et al. Their study revealed a significant increase in the Dose Area Product and investigating physician absorbed radiation dose with increasing patient BMI. In a study with 550 adult patients (age ≥ 15 years) to determine body-mass index-based effective dose determination in

commonly performed computed tomography examinations in adults by Deevband *et al.*; demonstrated that higher BMI contributes to an increase in patients absorbed radiation dose. Although their study was not specific for brain CT scan, further studies is recommended to establish the findings. Age and BMI in the index study showed a modest positive link, while age and cancer risk did not correlate, according to the research. This was consistent with research by de Basea *et al.* (2018) that found that ELCR varied across exposure age groups and did not consistently rely on age at exposure.

Comparison of the value obtained in this study with other studies, the values in the index study were lower than the values obtained in the study at the Netherlands. The reason for the variation could be in one part due to machine type used, and the slice number of CT scanner machine used which could not be ascertained from the study methodology. Secondly it could also be due to the fact that some of the studies were national studies with multi-center involvement necessitating the variation.

Limitations of the Study

The study was subjected to limitations such as long machine down time, high cost of investigation from the patient side, epileptic power supply, high cost of maintenance of the machine and uneasy access to TLD chips.

CONCLUSION

Patient absorbed dose measurements using TLD revealed that brain dose increased with the number of CT slices, with 64-slice procedures delivering higher doses than 16-slice, indicating that increased CT use may raise artificial radiation exposure in the population. The study revealed that males undertake CT brain earlier in age than females however, the absorbed radiation dose with its consequent, the effective doses was higher among the females compared to that received by males. The study found that mean effective doses increased with the number of CT slices.

Lifetime Attributable Cancer Risk was estimated at 3 per 100,000 population for the facility, indicating higher risk with increasing slices and absorbed dose. The study also concludes that; there was a lifetime cancer risk associated with the use of this ionizing radiation-based imaging modality with approximately 3 per 10⁵ population undergoing CT scan procedures could develop cancer in their lifetime. Furthermore, the study also concludes that the hereditary risk for the future generations of the sampled patients was found to 4 per 10⁶ populations. The findings emphasize that even low radiation exposure carries a potential malignancy risk, requiring strict caution.

Declarations

Ethical Consideration: Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the University of Port-Harcourt Research Ethics Committee.

Authors' Contribution

All the authors participated and were involved in the conceptualization of the study, collation of data, analysis and review of the study as well as the writing, and proof reading of the manuscript. The manuscript has been read and approved by all the authors and all the authors were involved in the conceptualization, collation of data, analysis and review of the study

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